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Research Article

**A DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH STUDY TO ASSESS
FREQUENCY OF VARIOUS RISK FACTOR OF CEREBRAL
INFARCTION IN THE PATIENTS OF BRAIN STROKE**¹Sana Khalid, ²Dr. Mustansar Mansoor Gill, ³Dr. Muhammad Ahmed¹Mayo Hospital, Lahore²The University of Lahore.³Allama Iqbal Medical College, Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: The knowledge about the dangerous features of mental failure and assessment of many kinds of dangerous aspects due to which proper treatment can be retarded are the main aim of this research.

Methodology: This descriptive research held at Mayo Hospital, Lahore (October 2016 to August 2017) at medical department. The selections of the participant have done from both gender with the age greater than 20 years. For mental disease confirmation, the computed tomography scan was used. As a result of obstruction and shrinkage of arteries, supply of blood and oxygen to brains stops and area of necrotic tissues.

Results: In this research, we documented 100 patients who have necrotic tissue in their brain. As listed in the table number one, all the patients got at least two risky features. High blood pressure or hypertension was the most repeated dangerous feature. More than 55% patients were found the sufferers of hypertension. The patients who were smokers and they were using more than 20 cigarettes per day from last 16 years were 30%. As discussed in the table number 2, different percentages of patients were found with different types of danger factors. The age limit for males is from 21 to 78 years and for females 24 to 78 years. 50 and 53 was the average age of males and females respectively.

Conclusion: Improper functioning of mind is the reason of more than 80% patients with brain attack. It is very commonly found mental disorder. The main causes of disabilities of human body is mental malfunction, It leads to worries and restless among the patients and as well as their close relations. As a result of this disease, patients and their families become burdened and restless. The risky factors that cause cerebral loss can be controlled. For the reduction of these factors, some significant steps should be taken.

Keyword: Necrotic, tissue, disorder, brain attack, danger factors, cerebral.

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INTRODUCTION:

Due to blockage or narrowing of arteries, blood or oxygen cannot reach to some brain part which remains for more than one day. Brain attack is a sort of mental disease. The reason for the more than 80% of brain attack is lost of cerebral work. All over the world, the second significant reason of deaths is brain attack. Every year, more than one lakh and fifteen thousand human deaths are because of brain attack. Every year, same number of people experience attack of brain but these are not subjected to death, As a result of this disease, fifty thousand fell a prey to disability. There exists same risky element which cannot be changed as civilization or society, the background of the family, gender and race.

High blood pressure, different disorders of heart, TIA's, cigarette smoking, the narrowing of arteries and lot of rest are different dangerous elements which can be reconstructed for metal violation. The knowledge about the dangerous features of mental failure and assessment of many kinds of dangerous aspects due to which proper treatment can be retorted are the main aim of this research. This objective also includes spreading awareness by means of proper education.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This descriptive research held at Mayo Hospital, Lahore (October 2016 to August 2017) at medical department. From the Hospital's emergency ward, 93% of the patients were choosen and 7% remaining from other departments. All the selected participants experienced brain attack for the first time. After the start of symptoms, they were taken to the Hospital with in one day. Mental disease which was due to obstruction of blood and oxygen in the aptness. For the medical evaluation including medical evaluation including B.P record and cerebral check, we claimed out different sort of testing. Some sorts of test which are taken on the participants are electro-cardiograph, serum figure, computed topographic scan and x-ray of chest.

Based on different origins, stroke has many definitions-stroke is a cerebral disease in which blood supply that brings oxygen to the every cell of brain

stops suddenly. This is due to blockage or obstruction of blood venal. For the very first time, the discovery of mental infarction is done through computed topographic scan [3]. As a result of obstruction and shrinkage of arteries, supply of blood and oxygen to brain stops and area of necrotic tissues forms in the brain [3]. For the retardation of this disease, there should be modification of some dangerous features. The intake of drugs by the patients is due to hypertension or some other causes. When B.P in the upper value, greater than one hundred and sixty millimeter Tess of mercury and in lower value, greater than ninety millimeters of mercury, this condition occurs.

For the assessment of diabetes in the patients, FBS was checked. By enhancing the values of cholesterol and triglycerides, we can check dyslipidemia. When the 0 waves in the electro-cardiograph changes inducing the pain in chest in past or at that moment, HD was observed. Some other risky features of this disease are fatness, smoking of cigarette, family background with this disease.

RESULTS:

In this research, we documented 100 patients who have necrotic tissue in their have necrotic tissue in their brain [1]. The age limit for males is from 21 to 78 years 50 and 53 was the average age of males and females respectively [4]. In both genders, the patients suffering from brain stroke were more than sixty years old. As listed in the table number one, all the patients got at least two risky features [2]. High blood pressure or hypertension was the most repeated dangerous feature. More than 55% patients were found the sufferers of hypertension [2]. The patients who were smokers and they were using more than 20 cigarelttes per day from last 16 years were 30 [2]. Diabetes was observed within 26% of the patients. Different percentages of patients were found with different types of danger factors [3]. Patients who were sufferer of this disease were mostly from clan. The mean time period for the patient's admission was not more than 10 days. We discharged 90% of our patients who were much healthy and could carry out routine activities.

Table – I: Frequency of risk factors of cerebral infarction in stroke patients

Risk Factor	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th
Number	19	23	37	15	6

Table – II: Frequency of risk factor of cerebral infarction in the patients of stroke

Risk Factors	Hyperlipidemia	Diabetes mellitus	Hypertension	Smoking	Obesity	Family history of stroke	Carotid artery stenosis	Atrial fibrillation
Number	30	26	55	31	15	12	22	25

DISCUSSION:

As the age increase, the risk of brain attack also increases. In this research, average age was 51.5 years for both genders. According to Sacco, RL report, the mean age for brain attack is 70 years. This age is much greater as compared to our research. The average age which was closer to our research was reported by AK here as 53 years. In Pakistan, the reasons of mental disorders are poor education, lack of knowledge among people and free hand to the risky aspects. Seventh decade was the most celebrated time for their disorder for both genders. Al-Rajah repeated some age for this disease. In our study, the most obvious risky texture is hypertension. As included by Ali-I and Al-Rajah, patients of hypertension were 55%.

About 38% of the brains attacks can be lessen with the control of high blood pressure and hypertension. After hypertension, mother significant factor which cause mental disorder is diabetes. This research demonstrated that 26% patients. Who were also the softeners of diabetes. As compared to the Qurushi's disorder were also the sufferer of diabetes. As composed to the Qurushi's discovery, it was much greater. In different studies for diabetes, different percentages are included. Another important dangerous factor is smoking. The quantity of cigarette used in one day tells the risk of smoking. As included in the tables, for different factors of risk, the percentages of the patients were different.

HD was discovered to be found in 34% patients. Almost similar amount was discovered by the Al-Rajah. Shrinkage or obstruction of mital veins is found in every patients and all were young. In our study, shrinkage of carotid artery which cause the stoppage of blood and oxygen to the cells was found in 22% patients. Almost similar value was discovered by change 45. The risky aspects for mental disease enhancer due to the extra work carried out with hands at work place fatty people which are passive are also best brain attack. The patients which have family background with this disease are 12%. As compared are performed in the same field, this percentage was little higher.

CONCLUSION:

Improper functioning of mind is the reason of more than 80% patients with brain attack. It is very commonly found mental disorder. Modification of main risky feature can be done through proper qualification of sufferer, high level of blood pressure, and a more rest risk are main causes contributed to cerebral malfunctioning.

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